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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the optical properties of monochalcogenide selenium (Se) and assesses its potential as a nonvolatile optical phase-change material (PCM). By leveraging spectroscopic ellipsometry and Raman spectroscopy, this research demonstrates that Se can undergo reversible, optically induced transitions between amorphous and crystalline phases. Compared to widely used PCMs, such as Ge₂Sb₂Te₅ (GST), Sb₂S₃, and Sb₂Se₃, Se exhibits lower melting and crystallization temperatures, indicating reduced energy requirements for phase switching, which could be indeed activated optically by green light irradiation. Optical characterization further reveals that Se combines a high refractive index contrast with minimal absorption losses in the near-infrared, particularly at telecom wavelengths. These properties make Se a promising candidate for low-loss, energy-efficient active photonic components and switching devices.

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Nowadays, we are witnessing the emergence of a new generation of photonic devices distinguished by advanced reconfigurability.^{1,2} Active reconfigurable photonic components enabled by the integration of nonvolatile phase-change materials (PCMs) represent a technological frontier in integrated photonics for applications such as neuromorphic computing,³ multilevel all-optical nonvolatile memories,^{4,5} programmable photonic processors,⁶ and laser-written photonic components^{7–9} among others.^{10–12} Nonvolatile PCMs enabling low power consumption and reduced losses are pivotal due to their ability to undergo reversible structural transitions between distinct structural phases, typically amorphous and crystalline, while maintaining their state without continuous energy input. Specifically, chalcogenide PCMs exhibit the capability to reversibly transition between amorphous and crystalline states in response to either suitable thermal stimuli for crystallization and melt-quenching for amorphization² or light irradiation at suitable wavelength and power.^{13–15} Consequently, the melting and crystallization temperatures, together with the irradiation wavelength and power required to exceed these temperatures, are key parameters for determining energy efficiency. Specifically, the lower the transition temperature, the lower the energy

input required for phase switching between phases, thereby enhancing the suitability of these materials for low-power photonic applications.

Chalcogenide materials, primarily tellurides and antimonides, have been the materials of choice, most notably Ge–Sb–Te alloys, commonly referred to as the GST family.¹ At telecom wavelengths ($\approx 1.55 \mu\text{m}$), GST materials exhibit significant absorption, with its extinction coefficient (k) increasing by nearly an order of magnitude during the amorphous-to-crystalline phase transition.¹⁶ Consequently, low-loss reconfigurable photonic platforms, such as those used for phase modulation, require PCMs with a large refractive index contrast ($\Delta n = n_{\text{cr}} - n_{\text{am}}$) and minimal Δk with low absolute k values upon phase change.^{17–19} Therefore, thoroughly characterizing the optical constants and the optical contrast during the phase change of PCM candidates is a mandatory initial step for evaluating their possible use in active photonics.

Elemental selenium (Se) has become of interest as Se doping enhances the phase-change properties of GST²⁰ in GSST materials as well as in Sb₂Se₃¹⁷ by reducing the extinction coefficient and increasing the optical bandgap.²¹ Metalloids monochalcogenides such as

selenium (Se) and tellurium (Te) are characterized by multivalency, providing a pathway to attain various phases and forms of the same element, each possessing distinct band structures and different optoelectronic properties. While Te is prone to oxidation,²² Se is inherently more oxidation-resistant due to the high activation energy for oxygen chemisorption (3.21 eV). Additionally, Se exists in several allotropic forms, including trigonal (t)-Se, rhombohedral (r)-Se, monoclinic (m)-Se, and amorphous (a)-Se.^{23,24} t-Se is the thermodynamically stable allotrope, and it is an indirect semiconductor with a bandgap of reported values 1.8–2.0 eV,^{25,26} while a-Se has an optical gap of 1.99 eV.²⁵ With near-zero absorption below ≈ 1.8 eV in both phases, and large optical bandgap (as shown in Fig. 1), Se is proposed to enable visible-to-near infrared (NIR) operation with potential for reduced losses at telecom wavelengths, motivating detailed investigation of its phase-dependent optical properties.

Furthermore, Se has a crystallization temperature with reported values between 40 and 90 °C.³⁰ At first glance, such a low temperature may raise concerns that the amorphous phase could spontaneously crystallize during uncontrolled heating in operating devices, potentially compromising reliability and data retention. However, Se remains attractive for phase-change processes activated optically or electronically rather than thermally. Notably, this transition temperature lies in the same range as that of the well-known phase-change material VO₂,^{34,35} whose metal-insulator transition (MIT) occurs at 69 °C and is widely considered promising for switching applications.

Additionally, the crystallization kinetics of Se, particularly in device configurations, still require optimization and may be slower than those of mature phase-change materials such as GST. This limitation could restrict reaching switching speeds in high-performance

information-processing applications, such as neuromorphic computing,³ multilevel all-optical nonvolatile memories,^{4,5} or programmable photonic processors.⁶ However, Se could still be interesting for applications such as laser-written photonic components,^{7,9,36,37} where energy efficiency and optical contrast are more critical than ultrafast modulation. In this case, Se lower crystallization temperature and reduced energy requirements are significant advantages.

Selenium-resistive switches^{38–40} were already reported in the literature in the 1970s, showing that the resistivity of crystalline selenium is $10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}$, while that of amorphous selenium is greater than $10^{12} \Omega \text{ cm}$, giving an upper limit for the (off/on) ratio of order 10^7 . Nevertheless, to our knowledge, no study, other than that of Huang *et al.*,²⁷ has reported Se as an optical PCM for reconfigurable photonic platforms, nor systematically studied the refractive index change upon phase transition. Previous studies have generally examined the optical constants of each phase independently, without analyzing the phase-dependent contrast critical for photonic functionality. In optical PCMs, alternatives to GST are being explored to reduce intrinsic losses.¹⁸ Among the most promising low-loss candidates, Sb₂S₃ and Sb₂Se₃ have been proposed due to their large refractive index contrast Δn between the amorphous and crystalline phases while maintaining a negligible extinction coefficient k in the near-infrared.^{17,41} These semiconductors have bandgaps of approximately 1.7–2 eV and 1–1.2 eV, respectively,^{42,43} enabling transparency at telecom wavelengths. In this respect, Se is also a semiconducting material with a bandgap $E_g \approx 2$ eV [see Fig. 1(a)], thus becoming a possible candidate for low-loss optical PCM material in the visible as well as in the near-infrared region.^{44,45}

Finally, comparison of the melting (T_m) and crystallization (T_c) temperatures of Se^{28–30} with those of Sb₂S₃,^{29,31,32} Sb₂Se₃,^{17,29} and GSST and GST³³ [Fig. 1(b)] highlights that Se's lower transition temperatures reduce the energy required for phase switching, offering an additional advantage for low-power photonic applications. Combined with its broadband refractive index contrast, near-zero absorption, and chemical stability, these properties make Se a strong candidate for energy-efficient, reconfigurable photonic devices, particularly in applications where ultrafast switching is not the primary constraint.

This study investigates the phase transition behavior of Se thin films by employing spectroscopic ellipsometry to thoroughly characterize its optical properties. Raman spectroscopy is utilized to monitor and analyze the optically induced transition between the amorphous and crystalline phases of Se. The research demonstrates reversible switching between t-Se and a-Se phases, highlighting its potential as an optical PCM.

The investigated Se thin films were deposited on Corning glass substrates by chemical transport of 99.99% Se powders in an He flow of 50 sccm in a tubular quartz reactor at a pressure of 0.2 Torr. For the deposition of amorphous selenium, a-Se, the substrate temperature was kept approximately at room temperature, while polycrystalline t-Se was deposited with the substrate kept at 150 °C. The thickness and the optical properties of films were measured by spectroscopic ellipsometry (Horiba-UVISEL) in the range 0.75–6.50 eV and at an angle of incidence of 70°. Microstructure and phase-change dynamics were investigated by Raman spectroscopy (LabRAM-Horiba) using a green laser at 533 nm.

The unit cell of t-Se contains three atoms arranged in a spiral chain along the *c*-axis, leading to a highly anisotropic crystalline

FIG. 1. Optical bandgap²⁷ (a) and crystallization and melting temperature (T_c and T_m) (b) of mono-elemental Se^{28–30} compared to common PCMs Sb₂S₃,^{29,31,32} Sb₂Se₃,^{17,29} GSST, and GST.³³

FIG. 2. (a) Unit cell of trigonal selenium (t-Se). (b) Sketch of the Raman modes of amorphous and trigonal selenium thin films (≈ 500 nm thick) were measured using a 532 nm laser. The images show the deposited films: amorphous Se (top) and trigonal Se (bottom), corresponding to the films where the Raman spectra were acquired.

FIG. 3. Ellipsometric fitting of the pseudo-dielectric function, $\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + i\epsilon_2$, measured on deposited a-Se thin films (a) using an ensemble of two Tauc-Lorentz oscillators and (b) using the Innami *et al.*⁴⁹ dielectric function for comparison. The inset in (a) shows a a-Se sample with the ellipsometric probing spot on it. As insets, the multilayer models used for the fitting is sketched. (c) Dielectric function and (d) refractive index obtained from our Tauc-Lorentz model and the values reported by Innami *et al.*⁴⁹

FIG. 4. Real and imaginary parts of the (a) and (b) dielectric function and (c) and (d) refractive index of a-Se (values reported by Innami *et al.*⁴⁹ and from this work) and single crystal t-Se ($E \parallel c$ and $E \perp c$ orientations)⁴⁵ as well as their effective medium as representation of polycrystalline t-Se. (e) Real and (f) imaginary refractive index contrast, Δn and Δk , between a-Se (values reported by Innami *et al.*⁴⁹ and from this work) and t-Se ($E \parallel c$, $E \perp c$, and polycrystalline approximation).

structure. Besides the covalent chemical bonds between the atoms in the chain structure, weaker van der Waals forces dictate the interchain interactions as shown in Fig. 2(a). As the intermolecular distances are shorter than the der Waals distances, it is deduced that weak attraction of covalent character exists between neighboring chains.⁴⁶ Figure 2(c) shows the Raman spectrum measured on our polycrystalline t-Se film. t-Se has D_3 point group symmetry, and group theory predicts a non-degenerate A_1 Raman active mode at 237 cm^{-1} and a doubly degenerate E Raman mode at 143 and 233 cm^{-1} . As shown in Fig. 2(b), the A_1 Raman mode corresponds to a symmetric breathing mode whereas the E modes are assigned to an asymmetric breathing mode and a rotation about x - or y -axis of the chain.⁴⁷ Polarized Raman measurements by Mooradian and Wright⁴⁸ revealed that for the laser polarized perpendicular to the plane of scattering, only the two E modes are present, while for the laser polarized parallel to the plane of scattering, only the A_1 mode is prominent. The polycrystallinity of t-Se films was confirmed by XRD analysis showing peaks at 2θ values of 23.50° , 29.65° , and 43.67° corresponding to (100), (101), and (110) orientations (JCPDS card no: 06-0362).

The Raman spectra of a-Se have been subjected to a lot of interpretations and, at the same time, misinterpretations.⁴⁶ The Raman

spectrum of amorphous selenium (a-Se) reflects a mixture of Se ring molecules and long chains, similar to those found in the trigonal phase. Figure 2(c) shows the Raman spectrum measured on the a-Se film, which features a broad peak centered around $\approx 250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This broad feature encompasses three contributions in the $220\text{--}280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range: chains of trigonal selenium (t-Se) at $\approx 234 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, disordered Se_n chains at $\approx 250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and Se_8 rings at $\approx 260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The inset in Fig. 2(c) shows that the films' color changes from red to blackish on increasing the deposition temperature from room temperature to 150°C .

Several authors have reported the optical properties of amorphous selenium (a-Se) using different techniques, including spectroscopic ellipsometry,^{49,50} reflectance,⁵¹ and quantum efficiency measurements.⁵² The real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function ($\epsilon_1 + i\epsilon_2$) and the refractive index ($n + ik$) of a-Se as obtained by Innami *et al.* by spectroscopic ellipsometry in the $1.2\text{--}5.2 \text{ eV}$ spectral range are shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d).⁴⁹ Their results report a bandgap of 1.87 eV .

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show the experimentally measured pseudo-dielectric function $\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + i\epsilon_2$ in a-Se thin film. The pseudo-dielectric function is directly calculated from the measured ellipsometric parameters (Ψ , Δ) under the assumption of a semi-infinite,

FIG. 5. Real and imaginary parts of the refractive index of (a) crystalline and (b) amorphous PCMs Sb_2S_3 ,¹⁷ Sb_2Se_3 ,¹⁷ GST,³² and Se. For Se, we take the amorphous phase values reported in this work, and the polycrystalline approximation for the crystalline phase. (c) Real and (d) imaginary parts of the refractive index contrast (Δn and Δk) for the selected PCMs.

isotropic sample. It therefore represents an effective optical response of the film-substrate system prior to model-based layer decomposition.

We performed ellipsometric fitting using two different approaches. In the first approach, the data were modeled over the 0.75–5.0 eV spectral range using a four-layer stack [Fig. 3(a)] consisting of (i) air as the surrounding medium; (ii) a 2 nm thick oscillator layer to account for surface contamination and roughness; (iii) a 498 ± 10 nm a-Se layer described by a dispersion model with two Tauc–Lorentz oscillators; and (iv) a glass substrate. The bandgap derived from our model is 1.71 ± 0.12 eV. For comparison, we also fitted our experimental data using the dielectric function reported by Innami *et al.* [Fig. 3(b)], restricting the analysis to their available spectral range. This second model also consists of four layers: (i) air as the surrounding medium; (ii) a 1 nm thick oscillator layer for surface contamination/roughness; (iii) a 513 ± 9 nm Bruggeman effective medium layer composed of 51.8% a-Se and 48.2% voids; and (iv) a glass substrate. The dielectric function and refractive index obtained from our Tauc–Lorentz model are compared with the values reported by Innami *et al.*⁴⁹ in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d), suggesting that our a-Se likely has a lower density, and highlighting that the dielectric function of a-Se is not unique, but depends on its microstructure, specifically the relative fraction of Se chains and rings.

The anisotropic crystalline structure of trigonal selenium (t-Se) gives rise to birefringence, with the optical axis aligned parallel to the c -axis. Consequently, two distinct dielectric functions (or refractive indices) are defined: one for light polarized parallel to the c -axis ($\mathbf{E} \parallel c$, extraordinary) and another for light polarized perpendicular to the c -axis ($\mathbf{E} \perp c$, ordinary). For the latter case, the optical properties are identical for light polarization parallel to the a - and b -axes ($\mathbf{E} \parallel a$, $\mathbf{E} \parallel b$).⁴⁵ The real and an imaginary parts of both dielectric functions and refractive indices are shown in

Figs. 4(a) and 4(b). Additionally, a effective medium ($\epsilon_{poly} = 2/3\epsilon_{E \perp c} + 1/3\epsilon_{E \parallel c}$) is also plotted as an approximation for the refractive index of polycrystalline t-Se with randomly oriented domains. From the refractive index values of a-Se and t-Se shown in Figs. 4(c) and 4(d), the refractive index contrast ($\Delta n = n_{cr} - n_{am}$ and $\Delta k = k_{cr} - k_{am}$) is extracted, as summarized in Figs. 4(e) and 4(f). This contrast constitutes a key figure of merit for evaluating the performance of a material as an optical phase-change material (PCM). Below ≈ 1.8 eV, where $\Delta k = 0$ and $k = 0$, the resulting refractive index contrast reaches $\Delta n \approx 0.8$ – 2.0 for the polycrystalline approximation, depending on whether the amorphous refractive index is taken from the values reported by Innami *et al.*⁴⁹ or from those measured in this work. This analysis is restricted to the spectral range covered by Innami *et al.*,⁴⁹ which limits the accessible energy window for direct comparison.

To enable a rigorous assessment of Se as an optical PCM, Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) compares its refractive index values, obtained from our dispersion model, with those of well-established PCMs Sb_2S_3 , Sb_2Se_3 , and GST. All Sb-based chalcogenides and Se exhibit a low-loss spectral region where the extinction coefficient k is negligible in both amorphous and crystalline states. For Se and Sb_2S_3 , this transparent window extends into the visible range, whereas for Sb_2Se_3 it shifts toward the near-infrared. In the crystalline phase, Se and Sb_2S_3 display similar refractive indices; however, in the amorphous phase, Se exhibits an n value nearly one unit lower, resulting in a significantly larger refractive index contrast Δn upon phase transition. Sb_2Se_3 consistently shows higher n values than both Se and Sb_2S_3 , while GST, despite its high refractive index, suffers from substantial optical losses across the entire spectral range and lacks a transparent window. These phase-dependent differences in refractive index are more clearly highlighted in Figs. 5(c) and 5(d), which shows the refractive index contrast (Δn) and extinction coefficient change (Δk) between

TABLE I. Refractive index contrasts Δn and Δk at selected wavelengths of 633, 800, 1060, 1310, and 1550 nm for polycrystalline Se, Sb_2S_3 ,¹⁷ Sb_2Se_3 ,¹⁷ and GST.³²

		$\lambda = 633$ nm E = 1.95 eV	$\lambda = 800$ nm E = 1.55 eV	$\lambda = 1060$ nm E = 1.16 eV	$\lambda = 1310$ nm E = 0.95 eV	$\lambda = 1550$ nm E = 0.80 eV
Polycryst. Se	Δn	1.78	1.45	1.21	1.44	1.42
	Δk	0.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sb_2S_3	Δn	0.84	0.69	0.58	0.57	0.59
	Δk	0.27	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sb_2Se_3	Δn	1.12	1.28	0.94	0.95	0.76
	Δk	0.80	0.37	0.01	0.00	0.00
GST	Δn	0.35	1.20	1.89	2.12	2.19
	Δk	2.14	2.05	1.54	1.06	0.67

the amorphous and crystalline phases across the spectral range ranging from 0.75 to 5.0 eV.

Table I quantifies these trends by showing Δn and extinction coefficient change Δk of polycrystalline Se, alongside Sb_2S_3 , Sb_2Se_3 , and GST at 633, 800, 1060, 1310, and 1550 nm. Across all wavelengths, Se exhibits the largest Δn among low-loss chalcogenides. It also maintains a nearly vanishing Δk , especially in the near-infrared where k is negligible. For low-loss reconfigurable photonic platforms operating at telecom wavelengths, PCMs with large Δn and low k and Δk are highly desirable. Selenium meets these requirements, combining high refractive-index contrast with minimal optical losses. This

makes it a promising PCM for phase-modulation applications in the visible and near-infrared ranges. In comparison, GST shows similar Δn values but higher Δk . This limits its use in low-loss photonics components but highlights its potential for optical switches requiring strong amplitude modulation.

Reversible amorphization–crystallization phase transition experiments were performed using laser irradiation with an excitation wavelength of 533 nm, and the phase transition dynamics were monitored in real time by Raman spectroscopy, as shown in Fig. 6(a). The initial state consists of deposited polycrystalline t-Se layer as revealed by the Raman spectra, showing modes at 144 and 237 cm^{-1} . The micrograph of the t-Se layer shown in Fig. 6(b) displays its needlelike structure. Amorphization of the t-Se film was performed by laser irradiation for less than 5 s with a power of 50 mW producing clear changes in the Raman spectra. After irradiation, the broad feature centered at 250 cm^{-1} appears, consistent with a-Se, and supporting laser-induced amorphization. The micrograph after amorphization of a small region indicated by the red rectangle is shown in Fig. 6(c). After amorphization, the surface is covered by a red-colored layer, which is characteristic of a-Se (see inset of Fig. 1). To demonstrate the reversibility of phase transition, re-crystallization of the amorphized region was performed by continuous laser irradiation with a power of 0.02 mW. Spectra were taken with an accumulation time of 5 s to monitor the crystallization dynamics. As the irradiation time increases, the mode at 250 cm^{-1} diminishes, while the modes at 144 and 237 cm^{-1} , characteristic of t-Se, emerge and steadily grow. This reversible transition from the amorphous to the crystalline state can be attributed to the relatively low activation energy of the phase change, estimated at 0.5–1 eV/atom.⁵³

While our Raman measurements provide real-time evidence of the structural phase change and proof-of-concept of reversible switching on the msec timescale (and optimization of the switching time is subject of ongoing further work), a recent study by Yang *et al.*²⁷ supports our findings by demonstrating that Se amorphization can be achieved with 488 nm 100 fs laser pulses at 2 kHz repetition rate, and crystallization can be induced with 532 nm continuous-wave irradiation over several seconds, at different scanning speeds. Importantly, Huang *et al.*²⁷ showed that the material can undergo up to 10^6 reversible cycles, confirming that Se phases can be reliably and repeatedly accessed. These results reinforce and validate our observations of Se's optically accessible phase-change behavior, highlighting its potential for energy-efficient reconfigurable photonic applications.

FIG. 6. (a) Raman monitoring of the amorphization and crystallization of Se. Micrograph of CVD deposited t-Se (b) before and (c) after laser amorphization of different regions as indicated by the red rectangles.

In conclusion, this work identifies elemental selenium as a compelling candidate for reconfigurable photonics, fulfilling the key requirements of a low-loss optical phase-change material at telecom wavelengths. Selenium undergoes reversible, optically induced transitions between amorphous and crystalline phases under green-light irradiation, with the extracted optical constants revealing a broadband refractive index contrast ($\Delta n > 1$) and minimal absorption in the near-infrared.

Compared to established phase-change materials such as GST, Sb_2S_3 , and Sb_2Se_3 , selenium exhibits significantly lower melting and crystallization temperatures, pointing to reduced energy demands for phase switching and making it particularly attractive for low-power optical reconfiguration. While its relatively low crystallization temperature and slower kinetics may limit its suitability for ultrafast information-processing applications, these constraints are less critical for laser-written photonic components and programmable static optical elements, where energy efficiency, broadband contrast, and low loss are the dominant design criteria.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Yael Gutierrez: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Software (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Maria Losurdo:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (supporting); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (supporting); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in OptiXs at <https://zenodo.org/records/18229804>, Ref. 54.

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